

Article

Low Adhesion Due to the Wet-Rail Phenomenon: Influence of Particle–Fluid Interaction in Wheel–Rail Contact

Bettina Suhr ^{1,*}

¹ Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, Inffeldgasse 21/A, 8010 Graz, Austria; sadegh.salehi@v2c2.at (M.-S.S.); klaus.six@v2c2.at (K.S.)

² Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Brno University of Technology, Technicka 2896/2, 616 69 Brno, Czech Republic; simon.skurka@vut.cz (S.S.); daniel.kvarda@vut.cz (D.K.); radovan.galas@vut.cz (R.G.); milan.omasta@vut.cz (M.O.)

* Correspondence: bettina.suhr@v2c2.at

Abstract

The wet-rail phenomenon can cause low adhesion, which negatively affects railway operation. It is believed to occur when small amounts of water mix with solid particles on wheel and rail surfaces, e.g., wear debris or iron oxides, forming a dense suspension in the wheel–rail contact, leading to sharp adhesion drops. Mini Traction Machine (MTM) tests using water-based suspensions with different particles also show adhesion drops during water evaporation, which can be linked to the wet-rail phenomenon. While the physical mechanisms underlying the adhesion drop are unclear, it is hypothesised that rapid loading raises fluid pressure in the suspension, separating wheel and rail surfaces, reducing force transfer through particle contact, thereby reducing the suspension's shear strength. For verification, a coupled Discrete Element Method and fluid dynamics model is used to simulate a simplified MTM setting and steps towards full scale wheel–rail contact. During simulation of rapid loading, fluid pressure rises but remains negligible compared to applied contact stresses in all considered cases. Thus, it is unlikely that hydrodynamic pressure build-up within the suspension contributes significantly to the low adhesion observed. Future research should investigate additional mechanisms, such as reduced shear strength of deformed or crushed wet particles under high normal loading conditions.

Keywords: low adhesion; wheel–rail contact; dense suspension; Mini Traction Machine tests; Discrete Element Method; fluid dynamics; pore-scale finite volume method

1. Introduction

The wheel–rail contact is the extremely loaded interface between railway vehicles and track systems. It is responsible for carrying the vehicle load, transmitting traction and braking forces and guiding vehicles through curves. Wheel loads in the order of 10 tons and more are transferred to the rail via contact patches with a size in the order of a fingernail, resulting in contact normal stresses in the order of 1000 MPa. At the same time, tangential contact stresses in the order of 500 MPa are transmitted due to traction, braking and wheel-guiding forces. All this occurs in an uncontrolled environment, resulting in wear, crack initiation and propagation, for example, which require costly maintenance [1,2].

The aforementioned tangential contact stresses are determined exclusively by friction effects in the wheel–rail contact. The adhesion coefficient (AC) is defined as the tangential contact force divided by the normal force. Due to the uncontrolled environment and contact

Received: 17 March 2026

Revised: 11 May 2026

Accepted: 20 May 2026

Published: 22 May 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC BY\) license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

conditions, the AC varies significantly; it can reach values larger than 0.5 under clean and dry conditions [3–5], but can also be below 0.05, for example, under leaf-contaminated conditions [4,6–11]. The latter is referred to as low adhesion and can cause problems with traction and braking, and potentially lead to safety issues [12]. Interestingly, in railway service, there are contact conditions in which a low AC is desired, e.g., in wheel–flange contacts. Therefore, substances such as lubricants are applied to the contact either from the vehicle or the track side. Conversely, during traction and braking the AC at wheel–tread interface should be maximised to ensure safe and reliable vehicle performance. Under such conditions, in low-adhesion scenarios, sand may be applied to increase the AC [13–16]. However, in certain cases, such as when vehicles pass tight curves, friction in wheel–tread contacts should have a medium level (0.35). This is because, in such cases, high adhesion levels cause noise and contribute to the development of rutting corrugations on the rail. Therefore, top-of-rail friction modifiers are frequently used for such scenarios [3]. In summary, there is no single optimal AC level in railway operation; it depends on the operating conditions.

There are two reasons for low adhesion caused by the natural contamination of the wheel–rail contact that are frequently reported, discussed and experimentally investigated in the literature. One case which causes lots of problems, for example in the UK, is falling leaves in autumn in combination with water [4,6–11,17–19]. During repeated over-rolling, a so-called black leaf layer forms on the wheel and rail surfaces. This layer is visible to the naked eye and can result in ACs below 0.05.

The second case of low adhesion is the so-called ‘wet-rail’ phenomenon [20–22]. This is the more challenging case and is investigated in detail in this study. The literature suggests that naturally existing solid particles, such as wear debris or iron oxides, combined with small amounts of water (forming a dense suspension), are responsible for the low adhesion in this case. In [23], experiments on a full-scale roller test rig were carried out. Before the test, the wheel- and rail-roller surfaces were cleaned, and during the tests, small amounts of water were applied continuously to the wheel–rail contact. Torques were applied to both wheel and rail rollers, to keep the rolling speed constant and to produce creepage in the wheel–rail interface. Under certain conditions, low ACs in the order of 0.05 were observed. This effect was highly transient, meaning that it occurred only for a very short period during massive slip events. It was always accompanied by the formation of a dark shining third body layer in the contact band, consisting of water mixed with wear debris and their oxides. After stopping the water application, this third body layer disappeared in a very short period, underlining the transient nature of this phenomenon. Similar observations were made by Beagley and Pritchard [24], on a twin-disc machine. At the beginning of the test, water was applied to the contact once. During the test, the water in the contact mixed with wear debris, forming a lubricating substance, which led to a drop in the AC. Due to the continuous evaporation of the water and the ongoing wear process, the behaviour of this substance changed over time and with it the AC, explaining the typical transient nature of this phenomenon. After the water had completely evaporated, the AC increased back to its dry level; see also [25,26].

Although experiments are able to produce the ‘wet-rail’ phenomenon under lab conditions and contribute to a better understanding of it, it is still unclear which physical effects in the contact zone cause the AC to drop to low levels. Modelling could be helpful in this context; however, only a few modelling approaches focusing on the ‘wet-rail’ phenomenon were found in the literature. The WILAC model presented in [27] predicts the creep-force/creepage relationship dependent on the amount of water applied to the contact. This phenomenological ‘engineering’ model was parametrised with the data from the aforementioned full-scale roller test rig [23]. The model published in [28] is based on

the squeeze flow theory [29], in combination with rough surfaces (statistical roughness distribution); see also [30]. Furthermore, a model describing the transient nature of adhesion when a water–talc suspension is initially applied to a rolling contact can be found in [31]. While all these models are useful for predicting adhesion and its evolution as the water evaporates, they do not provide new insights into the physical effects occurring in the contact due to their phenomenological and macroscopic approaches.

This was the motivation behind this research. In [30], two explanations are presented how particles can cause low adhesion. “Solid contamination can be both sufficiently strong and pliable enough to support a wheel, yet have a low shear strength. When sufficient viscous contamination is present, however, a train wheel can be hydrodynamically lubricated with the resulting coefficient of adhesion being low”. This research focuses on the latter aspect and examines in detail the possible underlying physical effects. It is based on the idea, that a dense suspension forms in the contact zone when wear debris and iron oxides are mixed with small amounts of water. Due to the rapid loading in the contact zone, fluid pressure builds up in the suspension, resulting in partial or full separation of the wheel and rail surfaces. At the same time, the shear strength of this loaded dense suspension is significantly reduced because the forces transferred by particle–particle contacts in the suspension are significantly reduced due to the aforementioned fluid-dynamics effects. To verify or falsify this hypothesis, this work applies a Discrete Element Method (DEM) modelling approach coupled with a fluid dynamics model to the problem. This approach was chosen because it is assumed that particle–particle and particle–surface contacts contribute significantly to the load transfer between the wheel and the rail in the case of dense suspensions, which is not considered in Elasto-Hydrodynamic Lubrication (EHL) models for rolling contacts; see, e.g., [32,33].

In wheel–rail contacts, multiple hydrodynamic mechanisms may arise within the dense suspension, including squeeze flow due to rapid normal loading, entrainment lubrication driven by rolling motion, shear flow induced by creepage, and hydrodynamic effects caused by particle deformation and breakage or limited fluid escape pathways. The present study focuses specifically on the first of these mechanisms, namely the build-up of fluid pressure within a dense suspension subjected to rapid compressive loading. By isolating this contribution, the work aims to evaluate whether squeeze-induced hydrodynamic pressurisation alone can account for the low adhesion observed under wet-rail conditions.

The paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, experimental results from Mini Traction Machine (MTM) tests are presented for suspensions with different solid particle materials showing transient adhesion behaviour. The loading situations in the MTM tests and in the wheel–rail contact, together with simplifications made, are presented in Section 3. The next section contains details on the chosen simulation approach. In Section 5, simulation results of the MTM tests are presented, followed by Section 6, where simulations are extended towards full-scale wheel–rail contact conditions. The paper ends with conclusions and the future outlook.

2. Experimental Results

In this section, experimental results measuring the transient behaviour of adhesion caused by suspensions are summarised. In the literature, frequently used test setups are twin-disc, such as in [26], or ball-on-disc, such as in [34]. In this study, the Mini Traction Machine (MTM), a ball-on-disc test, was used (MTM2, PCS Instruments, London, UK). All experiments were conducted at the Brno University of Technology.

In the MTM, a rotating ball with a radius $r_{ball} = 9.525$ mm rolls on a rotating disc with a defined creepage. The ball contacts the disc at a radius of approximately $r_{disc} = 20$ mm; see Figure 1a for a scheme. Both the ball and disc are made of AISI 52100 bearing steel (PCS

Instruments, London, UK) which has the advantages of high wear resistance, and thus a non-changing contact geometry and surface roughness. The ball is vertically loaded and the suspension is applied to the running contact using a micropipette after the dry run-in, and the evolution of the AC is recorded. The vertical load in these experiments was 16 N, corresponding to an average Hertzian stress of $\sigma_{av} = 510$ MPa, a rolling speed of 0.3 m/s and a Slide-to-Roll Ratio (SRR) of 0.05.

Figure 1. MTM testing. (a) MTM scheme [31]. (b) MTM results with talc-water suspension. (c) suspension meniscus [31].

To provide a more comprehensive picture of the measured ACs of suspensions, first, the ACs of the dry contact and pure water in the contact will be mentioned. In all measurements, the AC in the dry contact, i.e., before suspension application, is close to 0.6. While no measurements with pure water were conducted in this study, Galas et. al. [34,35] conducted such measurements using the same test rig as in this study. In [34], the same normal load, rolling speed and SRR value as in this study were used. After the application of 1 mL of pure water, the AC dropped to 0.3, followed by a slow increase to 0.5. As 1 mL of water is a considerably larger amount than will be considered, it is worth mentioning the results of [35], where the amount of the applied water was varied between 1 μ L and 10 μ L for different values of normal load, rolling speed and SRR. After water application, the ACs showed a sharp drop and remained low for some time before increasing back to dry conditions; minimal ACs were above 0.35 in all cases.

After these prerequisites, results are presented for water–talc suspensions. Talc can be present in the wheel–rail contact, as it is used in many top-of-rail products [34,36]. Moreover, talc is well addressed in the literature [31,34,37], as it is easy to see the transient effect in the measured AC with a pronounced friction drop during the evaporation of the water in the suspension. Talc particles had a size of 4.7 μ m and a flake-like shape.

Figure 1b shows a result from experiments with a talc–water suspensions (90 wt% water and 10 wt% talc) where 20 μ L of the suspension were applied. Immediately after applying the suspension, the AC drops from 0.6 to values around 0.4. It stays at this level for about 30 s. However, during this time, water evaporates, changing the solid particle concentration of the suspension flowing around the contact. Due to capillary effects, in this phase of the test, a so-called meniscus forms around the contact, which can be seen as a suspension reservoir in Figure 1c. After this period, the AC sharply drops to values below 0.1. After this low-adhesion phase, the AC starts to recover. In this phase, the contact dries out and the AC increases back to the dry level of above 0.5. The influence of the amount of applied suspension, as well as the percentage of talc in the suspension, was studied in [34] using the same settings for applied load, speed and SRR. In [37], the transient friction drop of water–talc suspensions were investigated by combining MTM measurements with optical

tribometer results. While the measured adhesion coefficient showed a comparable behaviour in both tests, the optical tribometer allowed to study the size of the suspension's meniscus and the particles in the suspension appear as dark shadings enabling conclusions about their flow path. After suspension application, particles are observed to flow preferably around the contact as the narrow gap between the ball and the disc makes it difficult for them to pass through the contact. Due to evaporation, the meniscus approaches the contact zone and particles are drawn in the contact. The thickness of the lubricating film increases and adhesion drops. After further evaporation, particles are expelled from the contact and adhesion is restored to the values of a dry contact.

For the wet-rail phenomenon, other materials showing a similar transient adhesion behaviour are more relevant. Both iron and iron oxides can be expected to occur naturally on the track due to wear and oxidation. Then, together with rain or dew, suspensions can form. Figure 2 shows the results from MTM experiments with suspensions of iron and black iron oxides (Fe_3O_4) consisting of 90 wt% water and 10 wt% solid particles. Suspension of three sizes of iron particles are compared in Figure 2a. For particles of 10 μm and 40 μm size, adhesion dropped to values around 0.1 directly after suspension application and remained at this low value until, due to evaporation, nearly dry AC values were measured. For the largest particles of 60 μm size, adhesion was around 0.3 after suspension application and dropped to 0.1 after 40 s of evaporation. Iron oxide particles were used at two different sizes of 50–100 nm (Sigma-Aldrich[®], 637106, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) and below 5 μm (Sigma-Aldrich[®], 310069, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). The adhesion shown in Figure 2b also shows a steep adhesion drop at suspension application, followed by a slow decrease in adhesion during evaporation to minimal values of 0.2 and 0.22, respectively. As the third material, suspensions of glass spheres with sizes between 9 and 13 μm (Supelco[®], 440345, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) were considered. As shown in Figure 2c, adhesion was reduced to 0.55 after suspension application, and after evaporation, a steep adhesion drop to 0.3 occurred. While this material does not occur naturally on the track, the spherical shape of the particles makes them easy to model in DEM simulations. As mentioned in the Introduction, a DEM–fluid dynamics coupled model is used to determine the role of fluid dynamics due to squeeze flow caused by rapid normal loading during the friction drop.

Figure 2. MTM tests with different suspensions: 20 μL of suspension applied with 10 weight percent (wt%) of particles.

3. Rolling Contact: Real vs. Simplified Loading Situation

Before starting with the description of the model, the loading situation in the wheel–rail contact zone is addressed. The upper illustration in Figure 3 schematically shows the actual loading situation of the rail. It is assumed that the rail surface is covered with a dense suspension and that this has no significant influence on the normal contact stress

distribution in the wheel–rail interface. This stress distribution is assumed to be elliptic according to Hertzian theory,

$$\sigma(x) = \sigma_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}, \quad x \in (-a, a) \quad (1)$$

with a denoting the Hertzian contact radius (for sphere on a plane) and σ_0 denoting the maximum Hertzian stress. For a constant rolling speed v_r , this equation can be formulated in dependence of the time $t = x/v_r$:

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_r^2 t^2}{a^2}}, \quad t \in (-a/v_r, a/v_r) \quad (2)$$

In the case of wheel–rail contact, the stress distribution is moving from the left to the right corresponding to the rolling speed v_r . Each point on the rail surface, indicated by the position x , undergoes the time history of the moving normal stress distribution. Points behind position x ($x + \Delta x$) undergo the same loading history, but with a time delay ($\Delta t = \frac{\Delta x}{v_r}$). This introduces multiple hydrodynamic effects arising within the dense suspension, including squeeze flow due to rapid normal loading, entrainment lubrication driven by rolling motion, shear flow induced by creepage, and hydrodynamic effects caused by particle deformation and breakage or limited fluid escape pathways. Taking this complex loading situation fully into account in a DEM–fluid dynamics coupled model would result in lengthy calculation times. Therefore, the present study focuses mainly on the build-up of fluid pressure within a dense suspension subjected to rapid compressive loading. Thus, the loading situation is simplified in this study, as shown in the bottom sketch in Figure 3. In this simplified approach, a box with a square cross-section (side length L) is filled with the dense suspension. The bottom (representing the rail surface) and the top (representing the wheel surface) plates are considered as impermeable, meaning that neither the fluid nor the particles can flow out, and thus a fluid pressure can build up. In contrast, the four side walls are generally considered as permeable, meaning that the liquid can flow out freely, but not the solid particles. This is a significant simplification, as it can be assumed that the rail is covered with a dense suspension even outside the wheel–rail contact area, making it more difficult for the water to be squeezed out horizontally, which would increase the fluid pressure in the contact zone. To avoid increasing the calculation domain and thus the computation time, two additional cases with partially or fully impermeable side walls are considered in Section 5.2. Fully impermeable side walls represent the case in which the highest possible fluid pressure is expected during the vertical loading of the dense suspension. Vertical loading is mimicked by vertical movement of the upper plate at a constant loading speed v until the average of the Hertzian stress, $\sigma_{av} = \frac{2}{3}\sigma_0$, is reached; details are described in the following section. One consequence of this approach is that the stress distribution acting on the upper plate does not represent a direct input, but rather a result of its vertical movement. The stress distribution and how it develops over time depends on the vertical loading speed of the upper plate, particle properties, fluid viscosity and so on, and differs from the loading history of the actual loading situation described above. While this simplified representation does not reproduce the spatially moving Hertzian stress field, it allows for the isolation of the effect of rapid normal compression on fluid pressure development as described above. The conclusions drawn in this work, therefore, apply strictly to this isolated mechanism. In the following sections, contact stress rates obtained from the DEM–fluid dynamics coupled model will be compared with stress rates calculated analytically for the actual loading situation.

Figure 3. Realistic and simplified loading situation in rolling contacts.

The analytical stress rate is obtained as time derivative of the Hertzian stress given in (2): $\dot{\sigma}(t) = \frac{d\sigma}{dt}(t)$. To obtain the mean stress rate, $\dot{\sigma}_m$, the averaged integral of this derivative is calculated:

$$\dot{\sigma}_m = \frac{v_r}{a} \int_{-a/v_r}^0 \frac{d\sigma}{dt}(t) dt = \frac{v_r}{a} \left(\sigma(0) - \sigma\left(\frac{-a}{v_r}\right) \right) = \frac{\sigma_0 \cdot v_r}{a} \quad (3)$$

For the MTM simulations, a Hertzian maximal stress $\sigma_0 = 769$ MPa, Hertzian contact radius $a = 0.1$ mm and rolling speed $v_r = 300$ mm/s are assumed. The corresponding mean stress rate in the loading state is $\dot{\sigma}_m = 2.307 \times 10^6$ MPa/s. The average of the Hertzian stress, which is applied in the simplified loading situation, see Figure 3, is $\sigma_{av} = \frac{2}{3}\sigma_0 = 510$ MPa.

4. Simulation Approach

The experiments outlined in the previous section are quite complex with the suspension at the contact forming a meniscus. While the simulation of fluid flow is usually done with CFD, particles are mostly simulated with DEM. Considering all of the effects observed in the MTM experiment—formation of the meniscus around the contact region with varying particle concentration including three phase flow effects, dense suspension running through the contact including particle breakage, etc.—within one overall CFD-DEM coupled model, this would involve enormous computational costs. Thus, the authors decided to split the overall problem into two sub-problems: (1) formation of the meniscus and movement of the solid particles within the meniscus and (2) running of the suspension through the contact. This research focuses on topic (2), so particle breakage is not considered. A simplified modelling approach is applied, as described below.

4.1. The Pore-Scale Finite Volumes Method (PFV)

In this study, the so-called pore-scale finite volumes method (PFV), as introduced in [38,39], is used. It considers a granular material that is saturated by an incompressible fluid. Fluid flow through the pores is governed by the incompressible Stokes equations, as viscous forces dominate over inertial forces (low Reynolds number). To reduce computational cost, the fluid problem is upscaled into a pore-scale finite volume formulation.

A pore-scale, finite-volume method is constructed from a regular Delaunay triangulation of the sphere packing. The triangulation partitions the pore space into tetrahedral control volumes and its dual Voronoi graph defines the pore network and the throats connecting neighbouring pores. The pressure is assumed to be constant in each Delaunay

cell. When the particles in the granular material move, they cause a volume change in the pores. Integrating the mass balance equation over a pore and using the divergence theorem gives that the rate of this volume change in the pore equals the sum of fluxes over the pore's throats. A linear equation between flux and pressure gradient is obtained by calculating the hydraulic conductance from its cross-sectional area and hydraulic radius (throat volume divided by solid–fluid interface area). In this way, using the pore network for a finite-volume discretisation of the continuity equation results in a linear system of equations for the pressure, involving the particle velocities on the right hand side.

Fluid forces on each particle are derived by integrating both pressure and viscous contributions over each particle surface. Pressure forces arise from differences in the discrete pore pressures on neighbouring tetrahedra, while viscous forces are estimated from the pressure drop across each throat using a simplified momentum balance. Together with buoyancy, the net fluid–particle interaction force is obtained and can be written as matrix multiplied by the pressure.

As described in [39], by adding the fluid force as the source term in the classical DEM formulation and inserting the expression for the pressure derived from the discretised continuity equation, only one system of equations needs to be solved. As both particle accelerations and velocities are involved in this linear system of equations, a semi-implicit scheme is suggested for its numerical solution. With given particle velocities, the pressure can be calculated in a second step. The method provides an efficient upscaling of Stokes flow while retaining pore-scale resolution of fluid forces. The PFV method causes considerably lower computational costs than a direct coupling of CFD and DEM.

The PFV method is implemented in the open-source DEM software Yade version 2052.2.0 [40,41]. It was used and extended in several publications: in [42], drainage of granular materials was simulated; Ref. [43] dealt with unsaturated flow through swelling particles; Ref. [44] developed a pore-scale thermo-hydro-mechanical model; and Ref. [45] studied capillary force evolution during slow-drying of a granular material.

4.2. Details of Simulation Setup

This study uses the Yade software [40,41], version 2052.2.0, and the PFV method is implemented such that the spheres and the fluid are placed in a cuboid geometry. The walls of the cuboid can move to apply mechanical loads on the system. On each wall, either a boundary value for the pressure or for the flux must be given. To obtain a unique solution for the pressure, a boundary condition for the pressure must be given in at least one point.

The simplified loading conditions considered in this work, which are derived from the actual loading situation in rolling contacts, were already described in Section 3. The key question is whether a simulation setup can be found in which the fluid pressure is of the same order of magnitude as the externally applied mechanical stress. This is a necessary prerequisite for the hypothesis that the build-up of a relevant fluid pressure in the suspension explains the measured AC drop.

In the MTM test, the ball of 19.05 mm diameter is loaded with 16 N on the disc. For steel material, this gives an average Hertzian stress of $\sigma_{av} = 510$ MPa and a Hertzian contact radius of $a = 0.1$ mm. The stress acting on the top plate will be referred to as external stress later on. In the PFV simulations, the same contact area is used but square-shaped, giving an edge length of $L = 178$ μm . The box height is set to be 35 μm as a first step. A schematic view is given in Figure 4 (see also Section 3 and Figure 3). The top and bottom of the box are impermeable, meaning that no flux boundary conditions are applied here. At all side walls of the box, pressure is defined to be zero; thus, the fluid can be squeezed out through these surfaces. Defining zero-pressure boundary conditions at the lateral walls enables efficient fluid drainage. This represents a limiting case of high

lateral permeability. To estimate the effect of reduced lateral permeability on simulated fluid pressure, two additional simulations with partially or fully impermeable side walls are conducted. Such reduced permeability of the side walls may arise from entrainment lubrication, effects from particle deformation or breakage, or limited fluid escape pathways. The external mechanical load is applied on the top plate by prescribing a constant loading speed v .

Figure 4. Schematic view of PFV boundary conditions, spheres and calculated pressure.

The sphere packing in the box is generated in a preliminary step using sample compaction at a nearly zero coefficient of friction. The sphere positions and radii are then saved to a file. The packing consists of 10,000 spheres with radii ranging between 1.6 μm and 3.2 μm and has a porosity of 0.39. These particle sizes allowed to resolve the box height with several layers. In the DEM part of the simulation, the Hertz–Mindlin contact law is used for particle–particle and particle–wall contacts, see [46]. The box walls are modelled as steel with a Young’s modulus $E = 200$ GPa, and the spheres are modelled as glass with $E = 40$ GPa. Both materials have a Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.22$, coefficient of friction $\mu = 0.2$ and the glass spheres have a density $\rho = 2550$ kg/m³, where material parameters are taken from the literature [47].

In the main simulation script, the sphere packing is loaded in the simulations and particles are allowed to rest for a fixed number of time steps. Then, the simulation of the PFV method is activated.

5. Simulation of Mini Traction Machine (MTM)

In this section, the first step is to conduct a parameter study, which also serves as a plausibility check for the simulation method. This allows us to study the influence of fluid viscosity η and the loading speed v on the simulated fluid pressure and the normal contact stress rate $\dot{\sigma}$. In a second step, further simulations with the viscosity of water at 20 °C, $\eta = 0.001$ Pas [48], are conducted to get closer to the MTM experiments.

5.1. Parameter Variation

In this subsection, the fluid viscosity, η and the loading speed v of the top plate are varied. For an easier comparison of results, all simulations end at a fixed loading path of 5 μm . As the top plate moves at a constant loading speed downwards, the sample’s porosity decreases linearly with the loading path from 0.40 to 0.31. The values of viscosity η and loading speed v used in the simulations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameter variation in simulations.

viscosity η [Pas]	0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 1, 3, 6, 10
loading speed v [m/s]	1, 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10

Selected simulation results for viscosities $\eta = 0.001, 0.1, 1, 10$ Pas and speeds $v = 1, 10$ m/s are shown in Figure 5. The external stress on the top plate, the stress rate and

the averaged fluid pressure are plotted over the path of the top plate. The averaged fluid pressure, p_{av} , is calculated by cutting the sample at half-height and averaging the fluid pressure over the resulting square cross-section. This value can be used to assess whether fluid dynamics effects play a role. If the fluid pressure is in the same order of magnitude as the externally applied stress, this is the case; otherwise, it is not. Stress-derivative results are smoothed with a moving average filter to avoid jumps in the signal after updating the PFV triangulation. The simulations in Figure 5a show nearly the same simulated external stress both for $\eta = 0.001, 0.1$ Pas and speeds $v = 1, 10$ m/s. Thus, the applied load is almost completely carried by the sphere packing. This is also confirmed by the plotted fluid pressure in the lowest subplot, where values are one to two orders of magnitude smaller than the external stress. The stress rate depends strongly on the loading speed, while results for both considered viscosity values are very similar. For loading speed $v = 1$ m/s, the stress rate increases linearly to 1×10^8 MPa, while for $v = 10$ m/s, after some initial oscillations, it increases linearly to values around 10×10^8 MPa. The results shown in Figure 5b refer to the viscosities $\eta = 1, 10$ Pas and loading speeds $v = 1, 10$ m/s. In the case of $\eta = 1$ Pas and $v = 1$ m/s, the final external stress of 325 MPa and the stress rate of 1×10^8 MPa are nearly the same as in simulations with lower viscosities, and the final pressure of 16 MPa is still low. Interestingly, simulations for $\eta = 1$ Pas, $v = 10$ m/s and $\eta = 10$ Pas, $v = 1$ m/s give very similar external stress and pressure results, only the stress rate shows again clearly higher values for the higher loading speed. The simulation with $\eta = 10$ Pas, $v = 10$ m/s clearly results in highest values for external stress, stress rate and fluid pressure.

Figure 5. Examples of simulation results of parameter study.

A summary of all results of the parameter study is shown in Figure 6. In the left subplot, the final averaged fluid pressure p_{av} (value at final loading path of $5 \mu\text{m}$) is plotted over the loading speed v for all considered viscosities. As expected, the p_{av} increases with both increasing viscosity and loading speed. For viscosities up to $\eta = 1$ Pas, the pressure–speed relationship is nearly linear. As viscosity increases further, so does the non-linearity of the pressure–speed relationship. The middle subplot of Figure 6 shows the final averaged fluid pressure in % of the external stress. Again, for viscosities up to $\eta = 1$ Pas, the relationship is nearly linear and becomes non-linear for higher viscosities. With increasing viscosity and loading speed, the amount of stress carried by the fluid increases. The results for final p_{av} and final p_{av} in % of external stress are nearly the same for simulations, where η is multiplied and speed is divided by the same factor. For example,

comparable results are obtained for $\eta = 0.1$ and 1 Pas with a loading speed of $v = 10$ and 1 m/s, respectively, as well as for $\eta = 3$ and 6 Pas with a loading speed of $v = 5$ and 2.5 m/s. However, this relationship does not hold for the simulated stress rate; see the right subplot of Figure 6. The simulated stress rates clearly increase with increasing viscosity and loading speed. Even at the lowest loading speed of 1 m/s, values range between 1×10^8 MPa/s and 2.5×10^8 MPa/s and are thus one order of magnitude higher than the theoretical estimated values.

The parameter study demonstrated the influence of viscosity and loading speed on external stress, averaged fluid pressure and stress rate, and also successfully verified the plausibility of the simulation method.

Figure 6. Summary of parameter study: final averaged fluid pressure, final averaged fluid pressure in % of external stress and stress rate at final loading path of 5 μm , all plotted over loading speed v .

5.2. MTM

The MTM experiments involve transient processes such as evaporation, meniscus formation, and gradual particle entrainment into and out of the contact zone. In contrast, the simulations do not address the transient process, but rather one effect that occurs during low adhesion, the rapid normal loading of a formed layer of suspension. Therefore, the MTM experiments are interpreted here as qualitative context for the observed adhesion behaviour rather than as a direct validation of the simulation results.

To bring the simulations a step closer to the MTM experiments with water-based suspensions, the viscosity of water at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\eta = 0.001$ Pas [48], is used and the vertical movement of the upper plate continues until the same external stress is reached as in the experiments, 510 MPa. All stress rates calculated in the previous section were considerably higher than the values estimated in Section 3 for the MTM loading situation. Therefore, simulations use the lowest loading speed of 1 m/s as a first step.

The PFV model described in Section 4.1 assumes a spherical particle shape. In most cases, this is a significant simplification. For example, the talc particles used in Section 2 are initially not spherical and deform and crush during the MTM experiment. In some of the experiments, glass spheres are used as particles. Glass is a brittle material and breakage is likely to occur when particles enter the contact. All these effects are not accounted for in the simulations, as this would cause enormous computational costs. However, some simulations with smaller spherical particles are conducted to investigate the extent of pressure increase caused by broken (thus smaller) particles. Furthermore, simulations with different sample height (varying third body layer thickness) are conducted to investigate the influence on simulated pressure. Additional samples are generated at a similar initial porosity, $p = 0.394$.

Samples of three different sphere sizes at a constant sample height of 35 μm are compared in Figure 7. The sample used previously consisted of 10,000 spheres with maximal radius of 3.2 μm , and the new generated samples consist of 100,000 and 200,000 spheres with a maximal radius of 1.52 μm and 1.22 μm , respectively. In the figure, the final values of the stress rate and averaged fluid pressure p_{av} are plotted over the maximal sphere

radius. For the three samples, the simulated final stress rate values are nearly identical. The influence of sphere size can be seen in the final fluid pressure, which ranges between 0.02 MPa and 0.07 MPa for the different samples. The secondary y-axis shows that p_{av} values are less than 0.015% of the applied external stress of 510 MPa, meaning that the granular material carries the external stress almost completely. As expected, the decreasing sphere size results in an increase in simulated fluid pressure.

Figure 7. Simulations of MTM setting for varying sphere packings of different sizes, sample height $h = 35 \mu\text{m}$: final simulated stress rate and averaged fluid pressure.

The analogous information is shown in Figure 8 for simulations with samples of differing height of 17, 35, 71 μm and the same sphere sizes of $r_{max} = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. With increasing sample height, the final stress rate decreases from $2.7 \cdot 10^8 \text{ MPa/s}$ to $0.7 \cdot 10^8 \text{ MPa/s}$, and so does the final averaged fluid pressure, which decreases from 0.1 MPa to 0.03 MPa.

Figure 8. Simulations of MTM setting for varying sample height, maximal sphere radius $r_{max} = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$: final simulated stress rate and averaged fluid pressure.

Due to the low viscosity of the fluid, $\eta = 0.001 \text{ Pas}$, and the loading speed of 1 m/s , all final averaged fluid pressure values are below 0.02% of the external stress. They are considered negligible, and in these cases, the granular material carries the applied external stress almost exclusively. To obtain realistic values for the stress rate in the simulations, the loading speed would need to be reduced. From the parameter study, it is clear that the simulated fluid pressure decreases with reduced loading speed. As the fluid pressure values are already negligible, these simulations are omitted.

The simulations conducted so far defined all four side walls as permeable with a zero pressure boundary condition, which allows for efficient fluid drainage. As mentioned in Section 3, this represents a significant simplification of the wheel–rail contact conditions, as it can be assumed that the rail is covered with a dense suspension even outside the wheel–rail contact, which could prevent water from being squeezed out and thus increase the fluid pressure in the contact zone. To estimate this effect, two additional simulations are conducted. As an extreme case of minimal drainage, the four sidewalls are considered

impermeable, with the exception of one cell with a zero-pressure boundary condition (at least one cell must have a pressure boundary condition). This simulation uses the packing of 10,000 spheres and loading speed of 1 m/s. The minimal drainage increases the simulated final fluid pressure from 0.03 MPa to 2 MPa (0.4% of the applied external stress). While this is a strong increase, such restricted drainage is rather unlikely. A second, and more realistic, case of restricted lateral permeability is that the four side walls are considered impermeable with the exception of four points on each side, where zero pressure is set as the boundary condition. In this setup, the final simulated fluid pressure is 0.12 MPa (0.02% of the applied external stress). Thus, simulations with reduced lateral permeability result in a higher fluid pressure. However, even under unrealistic low permeability, the simulated fluid pressure is still considered negligible.

Even though the simulations carried out are a strong simplification of the MTM conditions, they strongly indicate that the friction drop in the MTM experiments is not caused by hydrodynamic effects due to rapid normal loading. Even the aforementioned effects of non-spherical particle shapes, particle deformation, and particle fragmentation are unlikely to cause the fluid pressure to rise to a significant level. This is underscored by the fact that, when spheres are used, the porosity of the granular material is already at a very low level by the end of the vertical loading process. These findings were confirmed by additional MTM experiments at reduced rolling speeds. Figure 9 shows the results of tests in which the speed was reduced from 300 mm/s to 20 mm/s and 50 mm/s, respectively. The adhesion drop is similar to that observed at higher speeds, indicating that pressure build-up caused solely by rapid normal compression is unlikely to dominate the observed adhesion drop. Further possible mechanisms need to be found to explain the friction drop.

Figure 9. MTM tests with talc water suspension: 50 μL of suspension applied with 10 weight percent (wt%) of talc with variable rolling speed.

6. Towards Simulation of Wheel–Rail Contact

In real railway operation, contact patches are much larger compared to MTM conditions, although the maximum and mean normal contact stresses are comparable. Typical contact areas are in the order of 100 mm², whereas in the MTM case, they are around 0.03 mm². Due to the much larger contact area, fluid pressure is expected to be higher. In this section, the computational domain is enlarged stepwise and the increase in fluid pressure is monitored. As before, the fluid viscosity $\eta = 0.001$ Pas is fixed.

The packing for $a = 0.1$ mm contained 10,000 spheres; thus, using the same sphere sizes for a realistic contact patch size for railway operation, together with the PFV approach, would result in an extremely high computational effort. The computational effort can be reduced by exploiting the problem's symmetry and the application of symmetry boundary conditions for the fluid pressure. As shown in Figure 10, the computational domain is

reduced by a factor of 4. Two side walls of the reduced domain lay within the original domain. Here, for the pressure, a no-flux boundary condition is applied. The DEM particles are mechanically restrained by the side walls, which is not exactly the same behaviour expected from the original domain, but it is considered a valid assumption.

Figure 10. Simulated fluid pressure on original and reduced computational domain with symmetric boundary conditions applied.

This approach of using symmetry boundary conditions is validated in two test cases using a loading speed of 10 m/s to generate a higher fluid pressure. Larger sphere packings are generated by placing the 10,000 sphere packings side by side like tiles. In the first test case, results of a simulation with a 2×2 packing are compared to the 1×1 case with the symmetry boundary conditions, which corresponds in both cases to a Hertzian contact radius of $a = 0.2$ mm. The second test case is for a larger domain of $a = 1$ mm, where a 10×10 packing is compared to a 5×5 packing. Figure 11 shows the compared results for external stress, stress rate and pressure for both test cases. Only very small differences can be seen between the original simulation and the one with symmetry boundary conditions. At the beginning of the simulations, the pressure is zero, and with the onset of compression, an instantaneous jump in the pressure occurs. For larger contact sizes, values of a , this jump is larger, as well as the pressure increase during loading. The two test cases show the validity of the use of symmetry boundary conditions, which were used from here on in the study.

Figure 11. Symmetry boundary conditions tests for two domain sizes $a = 0.2$ mm and $a = 1$ mm.

The next step is to further increase the contact area. Figure 12a shows simulation results for $a = 0.2, 1, 2, 2.6$ mm and a loading speed of 10 m/s. For $a = 2.6$ mm the packing

consists of 1.7 million spheres. Due to the technical limitations of software packages used in the implementation of the PFV method, simulations of larger systems were not possible. While the simulated external stress and stress rate results are very similar, the pressure is influenced by the contact area as expected. For larger contact areas, the initial pressure at the start of compaction is higher, as the pressure increases during compaction. For $a = 2, 2.6$ mm, the final fluid pressure is 85, 135 MPa, respectively, already in the same order of magnitude as the external stress (17% and 26% of the applied external stress). For contact patch sizes corresponding to railway operation ($A = 98 \text{ mm}^2 \rightarrow a = 5.6 \text{ mm}$) the final pressure would be even higher. However, these results were simulated with a loading speed of 10 m/s, which results in values of the stress rate that are too large by a factor of 100. Therefore, an additional simulation for $a = 2$ mm and a loading speed of 1 m/s was conducted; see Figure 12b. As known from the previous parameter study, the stress rate is clearly reduced in this case down to $1e8 \text{ MPa/s}$, and also, the final pressure reduces from 85 MPa to 10 MPa (2% of the applied external stress).

(a) increasing size at const. speed of 10 m/s

(b) influence of speed at const. size $a = 2$ mm

Figure 12. Influence of domain size and loading speed on pressure.

As already mentioned, to simulate the fluid pressure representative for the wheel–rail contact, the contact area needs to be increased, and at the same time, the loading speed needs to be reduced to clearly below 1 m/s. Such a simulation would result in an enormously high computation time. Therefore, a different approach is chosen to estimate the pressure under these conditions.

As a first step, the influence of the size, i.e., contact area, and the loading speed on the final values of stress rate and fluid pressure is plotted in Figure 13. For this, additional simulations at $v = 0.1, 1, 5$ m/s were conducted. Due to long computational times, simulations with $v = 0.1$ m/s were conducted only for $a = 0.2, 1$ mm ($A = 0.125, 3.14 \text{ mm}^2$). For the stress rate, a linear dependency on the loading speed is seen in Figure 13a, while its values are nearly constant for changing contact area in Figure 13b. In contrast, the final fluid pressure depends on both loading speed and contact area. For a fixed contact areas, the final fluid pressure depends linearly on the loading speed, where the slope of the line depends on the contact area; see Figure 13a. The analogue behaviour is seen in Figure 13b for fixed loading speed values and varying contact area. Thus, it is chosen to estimate the final fluid pressure by a bilinear function of loading speed and contact area, as this is the simplest function fitting to the data. This bilinear relation is an empirical fit within

the simulated parameter range and its extrapolation to substantially larger contact areas involves uncertainty.

Figure 13. Influence of contact area, $A = \pi a^2$, and loading speed v on final values of stress rate and pressure.

The data shown in Figure 13 is now used to fit (bi)linear functions for the stress rate and fluid pressure. As the stress rate depends linearly on the loading speed, a simple line passing through the origin is fitted through the data and the fitted function is denoted as $\dot{\sigma}_f(v)$. The excellent agreement between data and fitted function is visualised in Figure 14a and can be quantified by an R^2 value of 0.999. For the pressure, a bilinear function, denoted by $p_f(v, A)$, is fitted to the data; see Figure 14b. To visualise the fit quality, $p_f(v, A)$ is evaluated in Figure 14c for fixed A and in Figure 14d for fixed v , showing the good agreement with the data, also with an R^2 value of 0.999.

Figure 14. Fitted (bi)linear functions for stress rate and final averaged fluid pressure. (a) fitted stress rate, $\dot{\sigma}_f$, over loading speed v : $\dot{\sigma}_f(v) = 1.34 \cdot 10^8 \cdot v$ [MPa/s]. (b) fitted pressure, p_f , over v and A : $p_f(v, A) = 0.07 \cdot v \cdot s. + 0.11 \cdot A + 0.66 \cdot v \cdot A$ [MPa]. (c) fitted pressure, p_f , over v for fixed A . (d) fitted pressure, p_f , over A for fixed v .

From the general considerations in Section 3, the mean stress rate, $\dot{\sigma}_m$, in realistic wheel–rail contact is calculated for two train speeds, v_{train} , using (3), with $a = 5.6$ mm and $\sigma_0 = 769$ MPa. Then, the fitted linear function of the stress rate in Figure 14a gives the loading speed in the simulation, v , which results in the mean stress rates $\dot{\sigma}_f(v) = \dot{\sigma}_m$. Finally, the fitted bilinear function for the pressure can be evaluated using v and $A = \pi \cdot 5.6^2 = 98$ mm².

$$v_{train} = 100 \text{ km/h} = 27.\bar{7} \text{ m/s} \quad \dot{\sigma}_m(v_{train}) = 3.8 \cdot 10^6 \text{ MPa/s} \quad v = 0.025 \text{ m/s} \quad p_f(v, A) = 14.2 \text{ MPa} \quad (4)$$

$$v_{train} = 300 \text{ km/h} = 83.\bar{3} \text{ m/s} \quad \dot{\sigma}_m(v_{train}) = 11.4 \cdot 10^6 \text{ MPa/s} \quad v_s = 0.085 \text{ m/s} \quad p_f(v, A) = 17.8 \text{ MPa} \quad (5)$$

From these estimations, even a high-speed train running at 300 km/h will cause a pressure of less than 18 MPa (3.5% of applied external stress). Thus, under the modelling assumptions adopted here, pore-pressure build-up due to rapid normal compression is not expected to be the dominant mechanism responsible for the adhesion drop in wheel–rail contacts.

While the above analysis provides an estimate of fluid pressure levels under increasing contact area and realistic stress rates, its interpretation requires careful consideration of the modelling assumptions. The extrapolation to full-scale wheel–rail conditions is based on an empirical relationship between fluid pressure, loading speed, and contact area derived within a limited parameter range. Its application beyond this range introduces uncertainty, particularly at lower stress rates and larger contact sizes. Furthermore, the present modelling approach isolates the squeeze-flow mechanism by considering a pre-existing dense suspension under rapid normal compression. As mentioned several times in the manuscript, other hydrodynamic and mechanical effects present in real wheel–rail contacts—such as rolling-induced entrainment, shear-driven flow, evolving particle concentration, and particle deformation or breakage—are not explicitly captured. These effects may influence both fluid pressure development and load transfer mechanisms.

Within this framework, the results indicate that fluid pressure remains significantly lower than the externally applied normal stress across all investigated conditions. This implies that only a limited fraction of the load is carried by the fluid phase, while load transfer is dominated by the particle network. Even under conditions of increased viscosity or restricted drainage, the relative contribution of fluid pressure remains limited. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as a bounding estimate of the contribution of squeeze-induced fluid pressurisation, rather than a complete description of the wet-rail phenomenon.

7. Conclusions and Outlook

In railways, the wet-rail phenomenon is frequently reported to cause low adhesion conditions. It involves small amounts of water and possibly naturally existing solid particles, e.g., wear debris or iron oxides, which could form a paste-like substance, i.e., a dense suspension in the wheel–rail contact. Several experimental setups, where suspensions are applied, e.g., in full-scale, twin-disc or MTM tests, show a transient development of adhesion involving a sharp drop to low conditions, studying different suspensions. However, the physical effects causing the adhesion drop were still unclear. This study investigated the hypothesis that rapid normal loading in a dense particle–fluid suspension leads to fluid pressure build-up, separating the wheel and rail surfaces fully or partially. The fluid pressure in the suspension reduces the normal forces transferred by particle–particle contacts in the suspension, which then reduces the shear strength of the loaded dense suspension.

Testing on an MTM machine showed a significant drop in adhesion when suspensions consisting of water and different types of solid particles were initially applied to the contact. Low adhesion only occurred for certain solid particle materials and for a short period of time, once most of the water had evaporated, resulting in a high concentration of solid particles.

A DEM–fluid dynamics coupled model was applied to MTM conditions to investigate whether fluid dynamics effects—build-up of significant fluid pressure in the contact zone—contribute to the adhesion drop during the fast loading of dense suspensions in the contact zone. Possible effects, e.g., from entrainment lubrication driven by rolling motion, shear flow induced by creepage, and hydrodynamic effects, that are caused by particle deformation and breakage or limited fluid escape pathways were not, or were only partly, considered in the model. However, the simulations revealed that, under MTM conditions, it is highly unlikely that fluid-dynamic effects from rapid loading significantly contribute to the friction drop. This was confirmed by additional MTM experiments with reduced rolling speeds, in which the same friction drop was observed as at higher speeds. The simplified setting in the simulations together with the experimental observations suggest that the observed friction drop in MTM tests is likely influenced by mechanisms other than squeeze-flow-induced pressure build-up, possibly by the reduced shear strength of the deformed and crushed (wet) solid particles.

Simulations with increased loading areas were carried out. These results were used to estimate the fluid pressure resulting from fluid-dynamic effects from rapid loading under realistic, full-scale wheel–rail contact conditions and rolling speeds of up to 300 km/h. Although the fluid pressure increased significantly under these conditions, it is still far lower than the applied loads, meaning that fluid-dynamic effects from rapid loading also seem to be negligible under these conditions. It is important to emphasise that this conclusion applies specifically to the isolated rapid compression mechanism considered here. Other processes present in real wheel–rail contacts, such as rolling-induced hydrodynamics, particle deformation and breakage, and time-dependent evolution of the suspension layer, are not captured in the present model and may play a significant role. The results of this study therefore provide a quantitative upper bound on the contribution of squeeze-flow pressurisation and help to narrow down the set of mechanisms that should be prioritised in future research.

Under the simplified conditions of this study, the squeeze flow mechanism cannot explain low adhesion. Future research will focus on testing and modelling the particle behaviour under normal and shearing loads, with the aim of better understanding the cause of the adhesion drop in the MTM experiments.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, B.S., M.-S.S., D.K., R.G., M.O. and K.S.; methodology, B.S., M.-S.S., D.K., R.G., M.O. and K.S.; formal analysis, B.S., M.-S.S. and K.S.; investigation, S.S., D.K., R.G. and M.O.; resources, M.O.; data curation, S.S., D.K., R.G. and M.O.; writing—original draft preparation, B.S. and K.S.; writing—review and editing, B.S., M.-S.S., S.S., D.K., R.G., M.O. and K.S.; visualization, B.S.; supervision, M.O. and K.S.; project administration, M.O. and K.S.; funding acquisition, M.O. and K.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was jointly funded in whole, or in part, by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) project PIN8512323 and the Czech Science Foundation (GA ČR, project GF24-14624L): Friction phenomena in rolling contacts caused by suspensions. For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC BY public copyright licence to any author-accepted manuscript version arising from this submission. The publication was written at Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH in Graz and partially funded within the COMET K2 Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Innovation, Mobility and Infrastructure (BMIMI), Austrian Federal Ministry for

Economy, Energy and Tourism (BMWET), the Province of Styria (Dept. 12) and the Styrian Business Promotion Agency (SFG). The Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) has been authorised for the programme management.

Data Availability Statement: The dataset newly generated during the current study is openly available in the zenodo.org repository, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20342276>.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Eden, H.C.; Garnham, J.E.; Davis, C.L. Influential microstructural changes on rolling contact fatigue crack initiation in pearlitic rail steels. *Mater. Sci. Technol.* **2005**, *21*, 623–629. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Garnham, J.; Davis, C. Very early stage rolling contact fatigue crack growth in pearlitic rail steels. *Wear* **2011**, *271*, 100–112. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Stock, R.; Stanlake, L.; Hardwick, C.; Yu, M.; Eadie, D.; Lewis, R. Material concepts for top of rail friction management—Classification, characterisation and application. *Wear* **2016**, *366–367*, 225–232. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Gallardo-Hernandez, E.; Lewis, R. Twin disc assessment of wheel/rail adhesion. *Wear* **2008**, *265*, 1309–1316. [[CrossRef](#)]
5. Zhang, W.; Chen, J.; Wu, X.; Jin, X. Wheel/rail adhesion and analysis by using full scale roller rig. *Wear* **2002**, *253*, 82–88. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Ishizaka, K.; Lewis, S.R.; Lewis, R. The low adhesion problem due to leaf contamination in the wheel/rail contact: Bonding and low adhesion mechanisms. *Wear* **2017**, *378–379*, 183–197. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Lewis, S.; Lewis, R.; Cotter, J.; Lu, X.; Eadie, D. A new method for the assessment of traction enhancers and the generation of organic layers in a twin-disc machine. *Wear* **2016**, *366–367*, 258–267. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Watson, M.; White, B.; Lanigan, J.; Slatter, T.; Lewis, R. The composition and friction-reducing properties of leaf layers. *Proc. R. Soc. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* **2020**, *476*, 20200057. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Zhu, Y.; Olofsson, U.; Nilsson, R. A field test study of leaf contamination on railhead surfaces. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2014**, *228*, 71–84. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Zhou, J.; Zhu, W.; Tian, C.; Wu, M.; Zhai, G. Experimental investigation of wheel rail adhesion under leaf contamination conditions. *Int. J. Rail Transp.* **2025**, *13*, 908–927. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Chen, H.; Furuya, T.; Fukagai, S.; Saga, S.; Ikoma, J.; Kimura, K.; Suzumura, J. Wheel slip/Slide and low adhesion caused by fallen leaves. *Wear* **2020**, *446–447*, 203187. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Olofsson, U.; Lyu, Y. Open System Tribology in the Wheel–Rail Contact—A Literature Review. *Appl. Mech. Rev.* **2017**, *69*, 060803. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Foo, C.T.; Omar, B.; Jalil, A.S. A review on recent wheel/rail interface friction management. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **2018**, *1049*, 012009. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Arias-Cuevas, O.; Li, Z.; Lewis, R.; Gallardo-Hernandez, E. Laboratory investigation of some sanding parameters to improve the adhesion in leaf-contaminated wheel-rail contacts. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2010**, *224*, 139–157. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Arias-Cuevas, O.; Li, Z. Field investigations into the adhesion recovery in leaf-contaminated wheel–rail contacts with locomotive sanders. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2011**, *225*, 443–456. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Skipper, W.; Chalisey, A.; R., L. A Review of Railway Sanding System Research: Wheel/Rail Isolation, Damage, and Particle Application. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2019**. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Vasic, G.; Franklin, F.J.; Kapoor, A.; Lucanin, V. Laboratory simulation of low-adhesion leaf film on rail steel. *Int. J. Surf. Sci. Eng.* **2008**, *2*, 84–97. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Lewis, R.; Trummer, G.; Six, K.; Stow, J.; Alturbeh, H.; Bryce, B.; Shackleton, P.; Johnstone, L.B. Leaves on the line: Characterising leaf based low adhesion on railway rails. *Tribol. Int.* **2023**, *185*, 108529. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Jaffé, J.; Lanigan, J.; Lewis, R. Field-based investigation of low adhesion leaf layers: Assessing layer initiation and environmental influences. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2025**, *239*, 116–131. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. White, B.; Lewis, R. Simulation and understanding the wet-rail phenomenon using twin disc testing. *Tribol. Int.* **2019**, *136*, 475–486. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. White, B.; Watson, M.; Lewis, R. A year-round analysis of railway station overruns due to low adhesion conditions. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2023**, *237*, 458–469. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. White, B.; Nilsson, R.; Olofsson, U.; Arnall, A.; Evans, M.; Armitage, T.; Fisk, J.; Fletcher, D.; Lewis, R. Effect of the presence of moisture at the wheel–rail interface during dew and damp conditions. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part F J. Rail Rapid Transit.* **2018**, *232*, 979–989. [[CrossRef](#)]

23. Buckley-Johnstone, L.; Trummer, G.; Voltr, P.; Six, K.; Lewis, R. Full-scale testing of low adhesion effects with small amounts of water in the wheel/rail interface. *Tribol. Int.* **2020**, *141*, 105907. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Beagley, T.; Pritchard, C. Wheel/rail adhesion—The overriding influence of water. *Wear* **1975**, *35*, 299–313. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Shi, L.; Ma, L.; Guo, J.; Liu, Q.; Zhou, Z.; Wang, W. Influence of low temperature environment on the adhesion characteristics of wheel-rail contact. *Tribol. Int.* **2018**, *127*, 59–68. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Gutsulyak, D.V.; Stanlake, L.J.E.; Qi, H. Twin disc evaluation of third body materials in the wheel/rail interface. *Tribol.—Mater. Surf. Interfaces* **2021**, *15*, 115–126. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Trummer, G.; Buckley-Johnstone, L.; Voltr, P.; Meierhofer, A.; Lewis, R.; Six, K. Wheel-rail creep force model for predicting water induced low adhesion phenomena. *Tribol. Int.* **2017**, *109*, 409–415. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Buckley-Johnstone, L.; Trummer, G.; Voltr, P.; Meierhofer, A.; Six, K.; Fletcher, D.; Lewis, R. Assessing the impact of small amounts of water and iron oxides on adhesion in the wheel/rail interface using High Pressure Torsion testing. *Tribol. Int.* **2019**, *135*, 55–64. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Engmann, J.; Servais, C.; Burbidge, A.S. Squeeze flow theory and applications to rheometry: A review. *J. Non-Newton. Fluid Mech.* **2005**, *132*, 1–27. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Beagley, T.M. The Rheological Properties of Solid Rail Contaminants and their Effect on Wheel/Rail Adhesion. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng.* **1976**, *190*, 419–428. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Kvarda, D.; Meierhofer, A.; Six, K. Testing and modelling of transient adhesion phenomena in rolling-sliding contacts. *Friction* **2024**, *12*, 1016–1027. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Faraji, M.; Seitz, A.; Meier, C.; Wall, W.A. A Mortar Finite Element Formulation for Large Deformation Lubricated Contact Problems with Smooth Transition Between Mixed, Elasto-Hydrodynamic and Full Hydrodynamic Lubrication. *Tribol. Lett.* **2023**, *71*. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Fang, C.; Peng, Y.; Zhou, W.; Meng, X. A fully coupled finite element solution for the mixed elasto-hydrodynamic lubrication of finite line contacts. *Tribol. Int.* **2024**, *194*, 109530. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Galas, R.; Kvarda, D.; Omasta, M.; Krupka, I.; Hartl, M. The role of constituents contained in water-based friction modifiers for top-of-rail application. *Tribol. Int.* **2018**, *117*, 87–97. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Galas, R.; Omasta, M.; Lu, B.S.; Ding, H.; Wang, W.J.; Krupka, I.; Hartl, M. The low adhesion problem: The effect of environmental conditions on adhesion in rolling-sliding contact. *Tribol. Int.* **2020**, *151*, 106521. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Wu, B.N.; Li, J.X.; Ding, H.H.; Shi, L.B.; Song, X.X.; Guo, J.; Zhang, S.Y.; Wang, W.J.; Lewis, R.; Meli, E. Study on the optimization of solid particle additives in top-of-rail friction modifiers based on a twin-disc testing apparatus. *Int. J. Rail Transp.* **2025**, *13*, 928–948. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Omasta, M.; Six, K.; Kvarda, D.; Galas, R.; Suhr, B.; Krupka, I.; Trummer, G.; Hartl, M. On the transient mechanism of water-particle induced low-adhesion phenomenon. In Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Contact Mechanics and Wear of Rail/Wheel Systems (CM2025), Tokyo, Japan, 22–26 September 2025. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Chareyre, B.; Cortis, A.; Catalano, E.; Barthelemy, E. Pore-Scale Modeling of Viscous Flow and Induced Forces in Dense Sphere Packings. *Transp. Porous Med.* **2012**, *92*, 473–493. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Catalano, E.; Chareyre, B.; Barthélémy, E. Pore-scale modeling of fluid-particles interaction and emerging poromechanical effects. *Int. J. Numer. Anal. Methods Geomech.* **2014**, *38*, 51–71. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Smilauer, V.; Angelidakis, V.; Catalano, E.; Caulk, R.; Chareyre, B.; Chèvremont, W.; Dorofeenko, S.; Duriez, J.; Dyck, N.; Elias, J.; et al. *Yade Documentation*, 3rd ed.; The Yade Project: Geneva, Switzerland, 2021. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Angelidakis, V.; Boschi, K.; Brzeziński, K.; Caulk, R.A.; Chareyre, B.; del Valle, C.A.; Duriez, J.; Gladky, A.; van der Haven, D.L.; Kozicki, J.; et al. YADE—An extensible framework for the interactive simulation of multiscale, multiphase, and multiphysics particulate systems. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **2024**, *304*, 109293. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Yuan, C.; Chareyre, B.; Darve, F. Pore-scale simulations of drainage in granular materials: Finite size effects and the representative elementary volume. *Adv. Water Resour.* **2016**, *95*, 109–124. Pore scale modeling and experiments. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Sweijen, T.; Hassanizadeh, S.M.; Chareyre, B. Unsaturated flow in a packing of swelling particles; a grain-scale model. *Adv. Water Resour.* **2020**, *142*, 103642. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Caulk, R.; Scholtès, L.; Krzaczek, M.; Chareyre, B. A pore-scale thermo-hydro-mechanical model for particulate systems. *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* **2020**, *372*, 113292. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Pham, S.T.; Chareyre, B.; Tsotsas, E.; Kharaghani, A. Pore network modeling of phase distribution and capillary force evolution during slow drying of particle aggregates. *Powder Technol.* **2022**, *407*, 117627. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Thornton, C.; Cummins, S.J.; Cleary, P.W. An investigation of the comparative behaviour of alternative contact force models during inelastic collisions. *Powder Technol.* **2013**, *233*, 30–46. [[CrossRef](#)]

47. Härtl, J.; Ooi, J.Y. Numerical investigation of particle shape and particle friction on limiting bulk friction in direct shear tests and comparison with experiments. *Powder Technol.* **2011**, *212*, 231–239. [[CrossRef](#)]
48. Kestin, J.; Sokolov, M.; Wakeham, W.A. Viscosity of liquid water in the range $-8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* **1978**, *7*, 941–948. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.